

THE AGGREGATION LINGUISTIC INFORMATION FOR DECISION MAKING BASED ON EXPERTONS AND 2-TUPLES

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The aim of this paper is to analyze the suitability of representing linguistic information by means of 2-tuples and its comparison with the methodology of expertons for handling problems of decision-making in uncertainty environments. In these cases, the information is expressed in the form of expert opinions, in vague or linguistic terms. These methodologies would permit

operation with information stated in different domains (multigranular linguistic information). This gives it greater flexibility than other methods, such as those based on the Extension Principle or symbolic models.

The paper includes an example of a practical application, where the validity of the model is contrasted.

Keywords: decision making, linguistic information, 2-tuples representation, expertons.

1. INTRODUCTION

Processes of decision-making, especially in those cases where the decisions will affect the future, are characterized by the difficulty of rendering information available. This is because in novel situations what little information is to hand is often derived only from the opinions or judgments of people with some experience of the topic under consideration.

In such circumstances, it seems most appropriate to facilitate as far as possible the capture of all information that may be thought pertinent. To do so, mechanisms must be established permitting experts to state their opinion in the terms or expressions that are most familiar to them, without requiring the imposition either of a specific form of expression or of the number of values that must be used in statements.

These considerations bring with them a twofold need, firstly, the feasibility of setting up mechanisms in decision-taking processes that allow operation with linguistic information and secondly, the possibility of using methodologies permitting the carrying out of decision-making with information represented in differing domains of expression. In other words, it is a case of finding tools that will facilitate the handling of multigranularity linguistic information.

Among the methodologies applicable to add the opinion of experts is found the

method of the "expertons" (Kaufmann, 1987; Kaufmann and Gil Aluja, 1993), a topic dealt with in the second section. This method needs that the opinions are emitted in a same domain of expression, what implies certain limitations in its practical application. In these cases would be feasible the utilization of models based on the Extension Principle or Symbolic Models, but both need to submit to the results to processes of approximation that imply loss of information

Moreover, in view of the limitations of both, the third section offers an explanation of a model of linguistic representation using *2-tuples* (Herrera and Martinez, 2000, 2001), which makes the procedure for aggregating multigranularity linguistic information easier, without any need to subject results to processes of approximation implying loss of information.

Thereafter, even though the representation based on *linguistic 2-tuples* has its own aggregation operators, the fourth section of this paper will attempt to go further into the problem of aggregating linguistic information, raising the question of an application of *expertons* methodology. This leads to a proposal to link the two, putting forward a hybrid model which in order to permit succinct exposition will include an example as a practical illustration. In it, details will be provided of the operational procedures involved, allowing conclusions to be drawn about the usefulness and operational applicability of the model.

2. THE EXPERTONS METHODOLOGY

Expertons are a method permitting aggregation of the opinions of several experts. With this end, starting from the evaluations these experts offer, statistics are drawn up for all possible values, these depending on the scale used to obtain the evaluations. The statistics are subjected to a process of normalization as a function of the number of opinions available. It is precisely this complementary cumulative function that is termed an "expertons" (Kaufmann and Gil Aluja, 1993).

Supposed n expert, that emit its opinion upon a specific event in an endecadaria scale given in Table 1.

Table 1

Expert	Valuation
1	0.3
2	[0.4, 0.9]
3	[0.5, 0.6]
4	0.4

The corresponding statistics upon the 11 possible values and its statistical normalized data would give as a result show in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively. The corresponding expertón (the function accumulated

complementary) would be in Table 4.

Table 2

0		
.1		
.2		
.3	1	1
.4	2	1
.5	1	
.6		1
.7		
.8		
.9		1
1		

Table 3

0		
.1		
.2		
.3	.25	.25
.4	.50	.25
.5	.25	
.6		.25
.7		
.8		
.9		.25
1		

Table 4

0	1	1
.1	1	1
.2	1	1
.3	1	1
.4	.75	.75
.5	.25	.50
.6	0	.50
.7	0	.25
.8	0	.25
.9	0	.25
1	0	0

The expertons possess the monotone growing horizontal not strict, that is to say, the lower extreme to the left is smaller or the same as the top end to the right. Also possess the monotone to growing vertical not strict, this is, every number at the level a 's larger or equal to every number at the level a , if $a < a'$. At the level 0 has always 1. Mathematically:

$$\forall a \in [0,1]: a, (a) < a_2(a) \text{ en } [a^a], a_2(a) \quad (1)$$

$$\forall a, a' \in [0,1]: (a > a') \Rightarrow (a_1(a) \leq a_1(a'), a_2(a) < a_2(a')) \quad (2)$$

$$(a = 0) \Rightarrow (a_1(a) = 1, a_2(a) = 1) \quad (3)$$

For its application, the expertons method first requires selection of the scale on which the opinions of the various experts will be expressed. While this methodology can be applied whatever the scale chosen, it is essential for the several opinions to be supplied on the same scale. This implies imposing on the experts involved the domain of expression in which they must state their evaluations, with a consequent risk of loss of operationally in the application.

In view of this possible limitation, and in the light of the usefulness of representing language information as 2-tuples in context of multiple graininess of textures, in the following section the 2-tuples linguistic model is presented, whose joint utilization with the expertons methodology permits to correct said limitation.

3. THE 2-TUPLE LINGUISTIC REPRESENTATION MODEL

The model for representing linguistic information that uses as its basis of representation a pair of values or 2-tuple (Herrera and Martinez, 2000), is a language representation model founded on the concept of symbolic translation.

It may be defined as follows: Let $S = \{S_0, \dots, S_g\}$ a set of language items, and $P \in [0, g]$ a value obtained by a symbolic method operating with linguistic information. The symbolic translation of a linguistic term s , is a number whose value lies in the interval $[-0.5, +0.5]$ and encapsulates the "difference in information" between a quantity of information expressed by the value $p \in [0, g]$, obtained through a symbol operation, and the nearest whole number value, $i \in \{0, \dots, g\}$, indicating the index of the linguistic label (S_i) that is closest in S .

The representational model based on the concept of symbolic translation utilizes as its basis for representation 2-tuples, (t_i, O_i) , where $T_i \in S$ and $a_i \in [-0.5, +0.5]$, with t_i being a linguistic term and a_i the number expressing the value of the distance from the original result p to the index of the closest linguistic label (t_i) in the set of language items S , that is, its symbolic translation.

Use of a representation as explained above requires conversion of classic linguistic labels into their equivalents as a 2-tuple. For this purpose, with $s_j \in S$ being a language item, its representation by means of an equivalent 2-tuple is obtained through the function O :

$$\begin{aligned} O : S &\rightarrow (S \times [-0.5, +0.5]) \\ O(S_j) &= (S_j, 0) \quad / s, e S \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Thus, starting from a numerical value p , $p \in [0, g]$ obtained from a symbol operation it is possible to work out the linguistic 2-tuple that would express the information equivalent to p by using the following function:

$$\begin{aligned} A : [0, g] &\rightarrow S \times [0.5, 0.5] \\ \Delta(\beta) &= (s_i, \alpha), \text{ with } \begin{cases} s_i, & i = \text{round}(\beta) \\ \alpha = \beta - i, & \alpha \in [-0.5, 0.5] \end{cases} \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where *round* is the usual rounding operator, s_i represents the label whose index is closest to p and a is the symbolic translation value.

The workings of the function A can be stated as follows: if it is supposed that there is a symbol aggregation operation on labels with values in the set of linguistic items $S = \{s_0, s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4, s_5, s_6\}$ and that the result of this aggregation is a value $p = 2.8$, the representation of this information through a linguistic 2-tuple is $A(2.8) = (s_3, -0.2)$, as shown Figure 1.

Thus, with a view to generalizing the process whereby a 2-tuple yields its numeric value, it is possible to take the line that if $S = \{s_0, s_g\}$ is a set of language terms and (s_i, a) a linguistic 2-tuple, it is feasible to obtain the

Figure 1

equivalent numerical value $0 \in [0, g]$ by means of the following function A^{-1} :

$$A^{-1} : S \times [-0.5, +0.5) \rightarrow [0, g]$$

$$A^{-1}(s_i, a) = i + a = 0 \quad (6)$$

Furthermore, it seems clear that the model representing information that is based on 2-tuples provides a set of operators allowing the operations of comparison, negation and aggregation to be carried out on these latter. Among the symbolic aggregation operators combining language information the LOWA operator is noteworthy. For their part, aggregation operators for 2-tuples extended from numeric aggregation operators have their origin in the aggregation operators in existence in the numerical domain (Yager and Filev, 1993), these permitting information to be aggregated in accordance with various criteria.

Similarly, it may be noted that use of the A^{-1} function defined above allows a linguistic 2-tuple to be converted into a number in the interval $[0, g]$, so that it becomes simple and easy to adapt any numerical aggregation operator to combine language 2-tuples. Among these the arithmetical mean or average, the weighted mean, and the OWA, the Or-Like S-OWA and the And-Like S-OWA operators are particularly important.

3.1. Aggregating multigranular linguistic information

In those decision areas where the evaluations used to resolve problems arising lie in the domain of language, situations occur in which these evaluations do not utilize the same set of labels, but belong to different linguistic sets, with differing graininess and/or semantics. In other words it is common for the information required to handle a problem to come from several sources, and possible for each of them in turn to have different grades of uncertainty and so need to use sets of labels of varying graininess, that is, be defined within a context of multiple linguistic textures. Hence the fuzzy language approach has a major limitation when it comes to carrying out processes of aggregation with multigranularity language information: there exist no standard procedures for normalization nor operators for aggregation for this sort of information.

The need, just mentioned, to aggregate information of varying graininess or texture, arises in most management problems. This leads to the operational proposal, set out in this section, which aims to unify this sort of information into a single domain of expression and more specifically to do so in those cases in which it is represented as 2-tuples.

In the specialist literature several approaches may be found to working with problems having multigranularity linguistic information (Chang and Chen, 1994). However, they tend to suffer from several drawbacks, either relating to the expression of results in domains other than the original, or having to do with information losses arising during the processes of calculation.

In fact, when information is expressed in accordance with varying criteria, it is common for a resolution scheme made up of two steps to be used (Roubens, 1997):

- a. An aggregation process, which combines evaluations or preferences to achieve a collective preference value for each alternative. This process has two phases: phase one being normalization, which consists of selecting a set of language terms within which the multigranularity linguistic information can be made uniform, and phase two, in which aggregation proper is undertaken, by unifying information with a linguistic aggregation operator.
- b. An exploitation process, which orders values according to a given criterion to get a solution set of alternatives.

a) Aggregation process

a.1.) Normalization phase. In the first stage of the process it is necessary to unify the multigranularity linguistic information into a single domain of expression, so that this, now uniform, information can later be combined.

For this purpose, the model proposed here starts from the initial suggestion made by Herrera and Martinez (2001), who considered the existence of linguistic contexts of varying graininess, denominated "linguistic hierarchies". These are governed by a series of rules and conditions, so that operations on multigranularity linguistic information evaluated in these contexts permit its unification into a single domain of expression without loss of information.

Linguistic hierarchies are composed of a set of levels, in which each level is a set of language items with a different graininess from that of the other levels in its hierarchy. Each level of a hierarchy can be written as:

$$L(t, n(t)) \tag{7}$$

where:

t is the number indicating the level of the hierarchy

n(t) represents the graininess of the linguistic set of level t.

Levels within a hierarchy are ordered by their graininess, that is, for two successive levels t and $t+1$ it will hold that $n(t+1) > n(t)$.

In accordance with the above, a linguistic hierarchy (LH) can be defined as the union of all levels t :

$$LH = \bigcup_t |J| (t, n(t)) \tag{8}$$

To analyze the construction of a linguistic hierarchy, keeping in mind that its hierarchic order is given by the change in graininess of texture in the sets of linguistic items on each level, the start point is a set of labels S on the domain U on level t , such that:

$$S = \{s_0, \dots, s_{n(t)-1}\} \tag{9}$$

with s_k language items in the set S and with $k = 0, \dots, n(t) - 1$.

To construct a linguistic hierarchy, the definition of S can be extended to permit the existence of various sets of linguistic items, each with a differing graininess on each level. For this, the parameter $n(t)$ is introduced into the definition of a set of labels, representing the graininess of the set on the level t where it is defined:

$$S^{n(t)} = \{s_0^{n(t)}, \dots, s_{n(t)}^{n(t)}\} \tag{10}$$

The methodology for constructing a linguistic hierarchy fulfils the following rules:

- Keep all the modal points of the assignment functions for all linguistic terms on a level when moving to the next level in the hierarchy.
- Make gentle transitions between consecutive levels. With the aim of building a new set S^{t+1} , a further term is added between each two terms of the set at level t . To carry out this insertion, the size of the support for the labels is reduced to reserve space for the new one, which is placed between them.

By way of an illustration, if a linguistic set is used with a triangular, symmetrical and uniformly distributed assignment function having an odd graininess value, in Table 5 the graininess needed for each linguistic set on level t is shown, depending on the value $n(t)$ defined on the first level (3 and 7, respectively).

Table 5

	<u>L (t, n(t))</u>	<u>L(t, n(t))</u>
Levell	L(1,3)	L(1,7)
Level 2	L (2, 5)	L (2, 13)
Level 3	L (3, 9)	

In general, it can thus be seen that the set of terms on level t+1 is obtained from its predecessor as follows:

$$L(t, n(t)) \rightarrow L(t+1, 2 \cdot n(t)-1) \tag{11}$$

In Figure 2 a diagram of linguistic hierarchy of 3, 5 and 9 labels is shown.

Figure 2

Moreover, once the operations involved in the construction of a linguistic hierarchy have been described, it will be necessary to establish a function permitting transfer of linguistic information from one set of terms to another without loss of information. This requires definition of the passage from one level to those immediately above and below it, with the aim of thereafter generalizing the procedure. For this purpose, the function for transformation of a term from level t into a term on level t+1 is defined as:

$$TF_{t+1} : l(t, n(t)) \rightarrow l(t+1, n(t+1))$$

$$TF_{t+1}(sP^{(t)}, a^{n(t)}) = \Delta \left(\frac{a^{t+1}(sP^{(t)}, a^{n(t)}) \cdot (n(t+1)-1)}{n(t)-1} \right) \tag{12}$$

For its part, the function for transforming a term from level t into one on level t-1 is defined as:

$$TF_{t-1} : l(t, n(t)) \rightarrow l(t-1, n(t-1))$$

$$TF_{t-1}(s^{*0}, a^{n(t)}) = \Delta \left(\frac{a^{t-1}(s^{*0}, a^{n(t)}) \cdot (n(t)-1)}{n(t)-1} \right) \tag{13}$$

The generalization of the operations just quoted, with the aim of allowing

transformations between terms from non-consecutive levels, can be attained by use of a recursive function based on the two functions given above. In this way, the recursive function for the transformation of a term from level t into one on level $t' = t+a$, with a $e \mathbb{Z}$ is defined as follows:

$$TF_{t'}^1(t, n(t)) \rightarrow I(t', n(f)) \quad (14)$$

- If $|a| > 1$ then $TF_{t'}^1(spO, a^{n(0)}) = TF_{t'}^{+|a|} \left(TF_{t-t'}^1(spO, a^{n(0)}), aa^{n(0)} \right)$
- If $|a| = 1$ then $TF_{t'}^1(spO, a^{n(0)}) = TF_{t'}^{+1} (spO, aa^{n(0)})$

The function for transforming terms between different levels in a hierarchy is idempotent, which guarantees transformation without information loss.

a.2.) Aggregation phase. This process consists of obtaining a value to represent the set of values it is desired to aggregate. The result of the process applied to a set of 2-tuples will itself be a 2-tuple. The resolution of this process may be approached by use of the two methodologies previously described, either through the utilization of numeric aggregation operators and their extension so they can work with linguistic 2-tuples, or through the application of symbolic aggregation operators to handle such 2-tuples.

The values obtained will permit the establishment of the best alternative within the given domain of expression. This is because, even if they may coincide in respect of the value of the label defining them, it is possible to pick out which is closest to each label from among the range.

Furthermore, if it became necessary to lay out the result on the basis of the original set of language items, so that all experts can be informed of the result in terms of their own domains of expression, all that is needed is for the transformation function to be applied, with the outcome of giving the collective value in all the initial domains.

b) Exploitation process

This process consists of choosing the best alternative, that is, establishing the greatest collective value for the set of alternatives obtained in the previous phase. In the two models considered in the second section, it was noted that several alternatives could yield the same final valuation, because of the process of approximation necessary for establishing the result in the original set of labels. In contrast, the current model, largely because of the sort of representation utilized, while making it feasible to establish the solution in the original context, facilitates choice among alternatives having the same solution, owing to the information collected in the symbol translation.

4. APPLICATION OF EXPERTONS TO THE PROCESS OF AGGREGATING INFORMATION REPRESENTED AS LINGUISTIC 2-TUPLES

Language information expressed in the form of linguistic labels permits the use of various types of aggregation mechanisms for this type of information. This section will thus attempt to weigh up the possibilities of applying the method of "expertons" (Kaufmann, 1987, 1992), as a suitable mechanism for handling information provided by experts, in those cases in which this information has been transformed into the corresponding language 2-tuples.

This paper raises the question of integrating the two methodologies into a single hybrid model. In this way it would become feasible to apply expertons in contexts of varying graininess with the expert opinions transformed in linguistic 2-tuples.

In this respect, with the aim of facilitating comprehension of the operations involved, an example will now be given as an illustration. For this, let it be supposed that a group of n experts (with, say, $n=3$) have expressed their opinions with respect to the future value of the market prices of a given range of investment funds. Let it be supposed that the estimate lies in the range [200, 230], and each expert states an opinion about this using the set of linguistic items easiest to use, for instance:

$$S^5 = \{VH, H, M, L, VL\} \quad S^7 = \{VH, QH, H, M, L, QL, VL\} \quad (15)$$

Here, the superscript number indicates the number of labels in the language set, with associated meanings on the following lines:

$$S^5 = \{VH=Very_High, H=High, M=Middling, L=Low, VL=Very_Low\}$$

$$S^7 = \{VH=Very_High, QH=Quite_High, H=High, M=Middling, L=Low, QL=Quite_Low, VL=Very_Low\}$$

Despite this, it is possible for expert opinions not to fit exactly any of the labels listed, so that the possibility of their answer being given by a pair of labels within each domain should be allowed. Thus, in the case under study, it is assumed that the information obtained from the experts is as given in Table 6.

Table 6

Expert	[200, 230]	Domain
e_1	M-VH	S^1
e_2	M	S^5
e_3	VH	S^7

Hence, the information available is seen as expressed in a context of multiple graininess, because the experts can use different domains of expression. Specifically, in the example given as an illustration, the domains are defined as

follow the table 7.

Table 7

Expert	
e_1	1(2,7)
e_2	1(1,5)
e_3	1(2,7)

In accordance with the above, on the basis of the comments previously recorded, the alternative of treating the information by means of a representation based on language 2-tuples is now considered. The evaluations provided by each of the experts can thus be stated in terms of the domains they use, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8

Expert	
e_1	$S_3^7 - S_6^7$
e_2	S_2^5
e_3	S_6^7

The need to normalize the information collected into a single domain of expression requires establishment of the set of language items that are to be used as a basis for unifying the information. In principle, practical reasons could lead to the use of the 1(2,7) domain, because it has been chosen by two out of the three experts. Nonetheless, the process of normalization can be carried out with any of the domains and it is even possible to undertake treatment in some further domain different from them.

In order to aid understanding of the technique of expertons as applied to language information in 2-tuples, in this example use is made of a domain of expression involving 11 possible linguistic labels [1(3,11)], which has the added advantage of permitting it to be assimilated to the eleven-point scale commonly utilized in expertons methodology. In this way, the process of normalization of opinions within the domain 1(3,11) by means of the transformation function will yield the unified values shown in Table 9.

Table 9

Expert	
e_1	(sV. o) - (s!J. o)
e_2	(sr. o)
e_3	(S;¿, o)

Aggregation of the information gathered can be achieved by use of the averaging operator for language 2-tuples. If this is done, assuming similar weight is given to the various opinions, the collective value for the a priori forecast would be given by the resulting 2-tuples:

$$(sj^1, -0'33) - (Sj^1, 0'33)$$

In this fashion, it is possible to establish the result in terms of labels from the domain chosen, or, if necessary, it would be feasible to use the transformation function to get the collective values within the original domains, as laid out in Table 10.

Table 10

1(1.5)	$(S_3^1, -0'33) \text{ st } 0'33$
1(2,7)	$(SL, 0) \text{ st } 0$

From the initial information it is likewise possible to proceed to application of expertons methodology, once the appropriate 2-tuples have been established and the information normalized into a single domain of expression [1(3,11)]. For this purpose, the statistics and experton corresponding to each 2-tuple obtained from the process of normalization are acquired as indicated in Table 11.

Table 11

$(S_1^1, 0)$	0	0	$(S_1^1, 0)$	1,000	1,000
$(s_2^1, 0)$	0	0	$(s_2^1, 0)$	1,000	1,000
$(sl^1, 0)$	0	0	$(S_2^1, 0)$	1,000	1,000
$(s^1, 0)$	0	0	$(s_3^1, 0)$	1,000	1,000
$(sP, 0)$	0	0	$(s^1, 0)$	1,000	1,000
$(S_5^1, 0)$	2	1	$(S_5^1, 0)$	1,000	1,000
$(sE^1, 0)$	0	0	$(SS^1, 0)$	0,333	0,667
$(s^1, 0)$	0	0	$(sp, 0)$	0,333	0,667
$(S_8^1, 0)$	0	0	$(S_8^1, 0)$	0,333	0,667
$(sE^1, 0)$	0	0	$(s_2^1, 0)$	0,333	0,667
$(s/O, 0)$	1	2	$(s/J, 0)$	0,333	0,667
Statistics			Experton		

From this information it is possible to determine expertons R^+ , as indicated in

Table 12, so that the values obtained may be used to calculate the mathematical expectation of the expertons. Its value is [0.667, 0.833], so that the operation would be the following:

$$200 + (230-200) \cdot [0.667, 0.833] \ll [220, 225]$$

It is easy to obtain the result that the mathematical expectation of expertons R^+ is [220, 225]. This permits tighter values to be obtained for the primary interval set up for the prices of the investment funds.

Table 12

$200+(230-200)(-)$	<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr><td>$(s\zeta',o)$</td><td>1,000</td><td>1,000</td></tr> <tr><td>(s'',o)</td><td>1,000</td><td>1,000</td></tr> <tr><td>$(s'g'.o)$</td><td>1,000</td><td>1,000</td></tr> <tr><td>$(s'j'.o)$</td><td>1,000</td><td>1,000</td></tr> <tr><td>$(sr.o)$</td><td>1,000</td><td>1,000</td></tr> <tr><td>$(Ss'.oj)$</td><td>1,000</td><td>1,000</td></tr> <tr><td>$[s'l'.o)$</td><td>0,333</td><td>0,667</td></tr> <tr><td>(s''',o)</td><td>0,333</td><td>0,667</td></tr> <tr><td>$(Ss'.o)$</td><td>0,333</td><td>0,667</td></tr> <tr><td>$(Ss'.o)$</td><td>0,333</td><td>0,667</td></tr> <tr><td>$(S'W.o)$</td><td>0,333</td><td>0,667</td></tr> </table>	$(s\zeta',o)$	1,000	1,000	(s'',o)	1,000	1,000	$(s'g'.o)$	1,000	1,000	$(s'j'.o)$	1,000	1,000	$(sr.o)$	1,000	1,000	$(Ss'.oj)$	1,000	1,000	$[s'l'.o)$	0,333	0,667	(s''',o)	0,333	0,667	$(Ss'.o)$	0,333	0,667	$(Ss'.o)$	0,333	0,667	$(S'W.o)$	0,333	0,667	=	<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr><td>$(si'.o)$</td><td>230</td><td>230</td></tr> <tr><td>(s'',o)</td><td>230</td><td>230</td></tr> <tr><td>$(s'l'.o)$</td><td>230</td><td>230</td></tr> <tr><td>(sy,o)</td><td>230</td><td>230</td></tr> <tr><td>$(sr.o)$</td><td>230</td><td>230</td></tr> <tr><td>$(s'j'.o)$</td><td>230</td><td>230</td></tr> <tr><td>$(S\zeta',o)$</td><td>210</td><td>220</td></tr> <tr><td>$(sr.o)$</td><td>210</td><td>220</td></tr> <tr><td>$(s'b'.o)$</td><td>210</td><td>220</td></tr> <tr><td>$(s'g'.o)$</td><td>210</td><td>220</td></tr> <tr><td>$(sU.o)$</td><td>210</td><td>220</td></tr> </table>	$(si'.o)$	230	230	(s'',o)	230	230	$(s'l'.o)$	230	230	(sy,o)	230	230	$(sr.o)$	230	230	$(s'j'.o)$	230	230	$(S\zeta',o)$	210	220	$(sr.o)$	210	220	$(s'b'.o)$	210	220	$(s'g'.o)$	210	220	$(sU.o)$	210	220
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In consequence, the operational procedure given above does demonstrate the validity of a representation with 2-tuples in handling information expressed as linguistic variables, as also the usefulness of joint operation of the expertons method with this form of representation. This permits the statement that it is valid to hybridize expertons with the model of language 2-tuples.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Over the course of this article has been possible to prove the validity of a representation of linguistic information by means of 2-tuples so as to handle decision-making processes in which the information available is determined by opinions given by experts. Likewise, as the underlying need in many management problems for aggregation of information has been noted, the various possibilities existing, both in the area of models based on the "Extension Principle" and in that of symbolic models have been considered. Since both these groups of models have the drawback of information loss during the process of aggregation, this work has looked at the alternative

offered by the methodology of expertons within a model of representation based on linguistic 2-tuples.

Furthermore, the possibility of working with information of varying graininess of texture has been considered. In this case a linguistic 2-tuples model, by means of the construction of linguistic hierarchies, facilitated operations in these circumstances. Thus, a detailed analysis was undertaken of the joint operation of a representation by 2-tuples and the expertons methodology. For this purpose an example of a practical application was set up, permitting demonstration of the fact that results obtained by applying a process of aggregation through the use of expertons leads to more accurate results.

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